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Is *Gambierdiscus* expanding its geographic range in the Pacific region?

Fig. 1. Top, macroalgae in lagoonal waters, Rarotonga, Cook Islands, from where *Gambierdiscus* sp. CAWD233 was isolated, and bottom, Phoebe Argyle sampling from eel grass in Tongatapu, Kingdom of Tonga.

The genus *Gambierdiscus* is known from tropical regions world-wide [1-4]. Species in this genus produce ciguatoxins (CTXs) and/or maitotoxins (MTX), which are regarded as the causative agents of ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) [1-4]. At the beginning of 2017, fourteen species of *Gambierdiscus* had been described [5-6] with three of these being described in 2016, an increase of nearly 30% in one year. The newly described species were *G. balechii*, *G. cheloniae* and *G. lapillus* [7-9]. Over the past few years, species which were previously only known in the Caribbean have been recorded in the Pacific [3], although this could be due to the greater research effort in recent years rather than due to introductions. Currently only *G. caro-*

linianus [6], *G. excentricus* and *G. silvae* [10] have not been detected in the Pacific region (Table 1).

Recently, genetically and morphologically identical isolates from as far apart as the Kermadec Islands (a New Zealand territory), the Cook Islands (Fig. 1) and the Kingdom of Tonga were determined to be unique. These isolates are maintained in the *Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae* (CAWD242 (Fig. 2), CAWD233 and CAWD250 respectively) and the description is currently in review. Identical DNA sequence data to this currently undescribed species have also been recorded for an isolate from eastern Australia, although the isolate did not survive [2]. If accepted as a new species

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Table 1: Geographic occurrence and toxin production (as determined by LCMS/MS) of *Gambierdiscus* species in the Pacific region.

Species reported in the Pacific region	Countries where reported	Toxins produced (LCMS/MS*)	References
<i>G. australes</i>	Cook Islands; French Polynesia; Hawaii (USA); Japan; Tonga	MTX MTX-3	Chinain et al. 1999 [26]; Kohli et al. 2015 [3]
<i>G. balechii</i>	Celebes Sea, Indonesia	(positive MBA)	Fraga et al. 2016 [7]
<i>G. belizeanus</i>	Australia (Queensland); Malaysia	(positive RBA)	Kohli et al. 2015 [3]; Leaw et al. 2011 [28]; Tester 2015 [22]
<i>G. caribaeus</i>	French Polynesia; Hawaii (USA); Korea; Republic of Palau; Thailand	(positive MBA)	Kohli et al. 2015 [3]; Litaker et al. 2009 [6] Tawong et al. 2016 [29]
<i>G. carpenteri</i>	Australia (New South Wales); Fiji Islands; French Polynesia; Guam (US territory); Hawaii; Mariana Islands	MTX-3*	Kohli et al. 2015 [3] Litaker et al. 2009 [6];
<i>G. cheloniae</i>	Cook Islands	MTX-3	Smith 2016 [8]
<i>G. lapillus</i>			Kretzschmar et al. 2016 [9]
<i>G. pacificus</i>	French Polynesia; Cook Islands; Republic of the Marshall Islands; Republic of Tonga; Vietnam	MTX-3	Chinain et al. 1999 [26]; Kohli et al. 2015 [3]
<i>G. polynesiensis</i>	Cook Islands ; French Polynesia; Vietnam	CTX MTX-3	Chinain et al. 1999 [26]; Chinain et al. 2010 [27]; Kohli et al. 2015 [3]
<i>G. scabrosus</i>	Japan	(positive MBA)	Nishimura 2014 [30]
<i>G. toxicus</i>	Australia (Queensland); Fiji Islands; French Polynesia; Guam (US territory); Hawaii; New Caledonia; Republic of Palau; Republic of the Marshall Islands; Vietnam	(positive RBA)	Kohli et al. 2015 [3]; Richlen et al.2008 [4]
<i>Gambierdiscus</i> genus†	New Zealand	NT	Chang 1996 [15]
<i>Gambierdiscus</i> sp. (isolates CAWD242, 233 and 250)	Cook Islands; Kermadec Islands (NZ territory); Republic of Tonga	MTX-3	Richlen et al. 2008 [4]; Smith et al. 2016 [8]
Species not yet reported in the Pacific region: <i>G. carolinianus</i>, <i>G. excentricus</i>, <i>G. silvae</i> [6,10].			

MTX: maitotoxin; MTX-3: putative maitotoxin-3; CTX: ciguatoxin; MBA: mouse bioassay; RBA: receptor binding assay; NT: not tested; †: Reported as *G. toxicus* but species unconfirmed.

*Where LCMS/MS results are either negative or unavailable results of bioassays are presented in brackets; **Australian isolates of *G. carpenteri* were negative for MTX by LC-MS/MS but positive by MBA [31].

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrographs of cells of *Gambierdiscus* sp., isolate CAWD242, from the Kermadec Islands: (A) view of cingulum and apical pore, (B) apical pore complex, (C) antapical hypotheca.

this will bring the number of *Gambierdiscus* species to fifteen.

A related species, originally described as *G. yasumotoi*, was reported in coastal waters of Northland, New Zealand, and in tropical eastern Australia [11-13]. It was later assigned to a new genus, *Fukuyoa* [14], and was reclassified as *Fukuyoa paulensis*. The three described species in the genus, *F. paulensis*, *F. ruetzleri* and *F. yasumotoi*, are not included in this discussion. *Gambierdiscus* was also reported as *G. toxicus* in northern New Zealand in 1995 [14], but without scanning electron microscopy or DNA sequencing data the spe-

cies identification is uncertain. However, the presence of *Gambierdiscus* [15] and *Fukuyoa* [11] in New Zealand indicates that Northland's coastal waters can support those genera with the risk that cells concentrations could increase to form blooms under favourable environmental conditions.

Climate change, in particular rising sea temperatures and changing currents, means that an expansion in the geographic range of *Gambierdiscus* is likely to continue and possibly accelerate [16-17]. Certainly average annual increases in sea water temperatures have been reported for both south-eastern

Australia and for New Zealand's coastal waters [18-19]. The appearance of *G. carpenteri* in the more temperate waters south of Sydney, New South Wales (NSW), Australia [16] may be explained by currents bringing cells from tropical Queensland to the warming NSW seas, but the adaptation of *G. carpenteri* to cooler temperatures may also contribute to the NSW records. The risk of CFP occurring in New Zealand's northern sub-tropical waters continues to increase and may impact on recreational fishing in the future and, potentially, the development of the commercial fishery.

Not all *Gambierdiscus* species produce CTXs or MTXs (Table 1). LCMS/MS allows specific and sensitive analysis of the targeted toxin groups and, based on our results, *G. polynesiensis* produces CTXs and *G. australes* MTX-1 [3,20]. However, all described species produce putative MTX-3. The toxicity of CTX is high by both intraperitoneal (ip) injection and by oral administration in mice, whereas MTX-1 is highly toxic by ip injection of mice, but much less so orally [20] and MTX-3 has relatively low ip and oral toxicity (R. Munday, unpub-

Fig. 3. Map of Pacific region showing the geographic distribution of *Gambierdiscus* species (2017).

lished data). The role of MTXs in ciguatera fish poisoning is uncertain and due to its low oral toxicity may only play a small part in toxic events [21].

A range of cell-based assays is available to detect CFP-related toxins, including receptor binding (RBA), Ca²⁺ flux, N2A and haemolytic assays [21] as well as whole animal assays (for example, mouse and larval bioassays [22-23]). Results of all these assays are not presented in detail here, but extracts of isolates of all species tested so far have shown a response in at least some of these bioassays, as can be seen in Table 1. These results suggest that compounds other than MTX-1 and CTXs may be produced by the species listed in Table 1. Other toxins known to be produced by *Gambierdiscus* species include gambieric acids, gambieroxide, gambierol and gambierone [20]. Despite the raft of methods available, the toxicity of isolates of *Gambierdiscus* still requires resolution to improve the knowledge of the functional biogeography of the genus.

The risk of ciguatera poisoning is clearly Pacific-wide and in some islands has caused many illnesses and even deaths [24]. The poisoning can have serious economic impacts, particularly on smaller Pacific Island communities [25]. The key producer of CTXs, *G. polynesiensis*, has been found from the far western edges of the Pacific (Vietnam) to eastern French Polynesia (Fig. 3) and is likely to be found further south with warming seas. Of course, the greater sampling efforts being undertaken are likely to add to the increasing detections.

Species such as *Ostreopsis ovata* and *Coolia malayensis* occur in the Cook Islands and French Polynesia, where *G. polynesiensis* has been reported. These co-occurring species with *Gambierdiscus* are also found in Melanesia, for example, Tongatapu, Kingdom of Tonga (Phoebe Argyle, unpublished data; Fig. 1) and the Fiji Islands. They also occur in Micronesia, for example, the Republic of the Marshall Islands, the US territory of Guam, and Tol-truk, Federated States of Micronesia [3]. This suggests that the environmental conditions may be suitable for the expansion of *G. polynesiensis* to these areas.

State-of-the-art molecular tools are likely to result in increased reports of all the known species of *Gambierdiscus* globally and assist in the discovery of new species. DNA sequencing data is critical for

descriptions of new species as conservative morphological differences can be difficult to identify. Quantitative PCR assays and metabarcoding are already generating considerably more data than can be generated by traditional methods. New species records are being made at new sites, for example, in Northland, New Zealand, and the Cook Islands (K. Smith, unpubl. data).

Ciguatera fish poisoning has been known in the tropical Pacific region for centuries, but the increase in species numbers and the expansion of the geographic range of *Gambierdiscus* species over the last few years (for example, *G. carpenteri* in NSW, Australia [31]; Fig. 3) suggests that CFP will also become of greater concern for more temperate regions in the Pacific in the future.

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References

1. Parsons M et al 2012. *Harmful Algae* 14: 107-129
2. Litaker RW et al 2010. *Toxicon* 56: 711-730
3. Kohli GS et al 2016. In: Botana LM et al (eds) *Climate change and marine and freshwater toxins, Anal Bioanal Chem* 408, Chapt 9
4. Richlen ML 2008. *Harmful Algae* 7: 614-629
5. Guiry MD & Guiry GM 2016. <http://www.algaebase.org>; searched on 07 Dec 2016
6. Litaker et al 2009. *Phycologia* 48: 344-390
7. Fraga S et al 2016. *Harmful Algae* 58: 93-105
8. Smith KF et al 2016. *Harmful Algae* 60: 45-56
9. Kretzschmar AL et al 2016. *J Phycol* DOI:10.1111/jpy.12496
10. Fraga S & Rodríguez F 2014. *Protist* 165: 839-853
11. Rhodes LL et al 2016. *NZ J Mar Fresh Res*, DOI.org/10.1080/00288330.2016.1270337
12. Rhodes L et al 2013. *NZ J Mar Fresh Res* 48: 303-310
13. Murray S et al 2014. *Harmful Algae* 39:242-252.

14. Gómez et al 2015. *PlosOne* 10(4): e0119676. doi:10.1371
15. Chang FH 1996. *Shellfish toxin update. Seafood New Zealand* 26, February 1996.
16. Kohli GS et al 2014. *Harmful Algae* 39: 134-145
17. Vergés A et al 2014. *P R Soc B* 281: 1-10
18. <http://climatechange.environment.nsw.gov.au/About-climate-change-in-NSW/Evidence-of-climate-change/Observed-Australian-climate-change>
19. *Ministry for the Environment 2016. Climate Change Projections for New Zealand. Ministry for the Environment, 127 pp*
20. Selwood A et al 2015. In: MacKenzie L (ed) *Marine and freshwater harmful algae. Proc 16th Int Conf Harmful Algae, New Zealand, Oct 2014. (Cawthron Inst & ISSHA) pp 66-69*
21. Lewis RJ 2006. *Toxicon* 48: 799-809
22. Tester P 2015. In: MacKenzie (ed). *Marine and freshwater harmful algae. Proc 16th Int Conf Harmful Algae, New Zealand, Oct 2014 (Cawthron Inst. & ISSHA) pp 44-48*
23. Argyle PA et al 2016. *NZ J Mar Fresh Res* 50: 444-456
24. Rongo T & van Woesik R 2013. *Toxicon* 64: 87-95
25. Rhodes L & R Munday 2016. In: Chisti Y & F Bux (eds). *Algae biotechnology: products and processes (Springer, UK), pp 301-316*
26. Chinain M et al 1999. *J Phycol* 35: 1282-1296
27. Chinain M et al 2010. *Toxicon* 56: 739-750
28. Leaw CP et al 2011. *Phycol Res* 59: 143-146
29. Tawong W et al 2016. *Phycologia* 55: 274-278
30. Nishimura T et al 2014. *J Phycol* 50: 506-514
31. Kohli GS et al 2014. *Harmful Algae* 39: 134-145

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Toxin production in lab-rat-diatoms (e.g. *Pseudo-nitzschia*) in the presence of copepods

From only 15 species in 1965, currently 49 *Pseudo-nitzschia* species have been described, of which 22 have the ability to produce the toxin domoic acid (DA), along with two *Nitzschia* species [1]. Both numbers are steadily increasing, illustrating an unexpectedly high diversity within the genus. Many of the

species are morphologically similar, e.g. species in the *P. pseudodelicatissima* complex, making identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species difficult. The high and steadily increasing number of toxic species emphasizes the importance of considering *Pseudo-nitzschia* species to be toxic for monitoring purposes, un-

less proven otherwise. One may in fact ask whether all *Pseudo-nitzschia* species are toxic - given the right circumstances as several factors such as physics and chemistry as well as biological interactions are known to affect toxin production [reviewed in 2, 3].

Toxicity in the laboratory and in the field – and copepods

It has been observed that *Pseudo-nitzschia* cultures tend to lose toxicity (toxin content per cell) over time in cul-

Table 1. Factors affecting production of DA in diatoms

Factor	Initial DA cell ⁻¹	Final DA cell ⁻¹	Times increase in DA content	Species	Ref
Copepod ¹	0.1	13.1	130.0	<i>P. seriata</i>	9
Copepod ²	0.1	4.15	40.5	<i>P. seriata</i>	9
Copepod ³	0.46	2.34	4.1	<i>P. seriata</i>	11
Copepod ²	0.36	1.98	4.5	<i>P. seriata</i>	11
Copepod ⁴	0.4	13.1	31.8	<i>P. seriata</i>	3
Copepod ⁴	0.1	2.6	25.0	<i>P. seriata</i>	3
Copepod ⁵	0.2	2.4	11.0	<i>P. seriata</i>	3
Copepod ⁴	0.0*	0-2	24.0	<i>P. obtusa</i>	3
Copepod ²	1.27	2.52	1.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	10
↓pH (8.4→7.9)	2 ⁶	10 ⁶	4.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	12
↓pH (8.4→7.9)	0.04 ⁶	0.07 ⁶	0.8	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	12
↑pH (7.9→8.4)	1.9	4.2	1.2	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	13
↑pH (7.9→8.4)	4.2	140	32.3	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	13
↑pH (7.9→8.4)	158	213	0.4	<i>Nitzschia navis-varingica</i>	13
P depletion	0.04 ⁶	2 ⁶	49.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	12
P depletion	0.07 ⁶	10 ⁶	141.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	12
P depletion	1.0	5.9	5.9	<i>P. seriata</i>	14
Si depletion	BD**	14.7		<i>P. seriata</i>	14
Si depletion	0.002	0.3	125.3	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	15
Si depletion	3.8 ⁶	11.9	3.1	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	16
↑temperature	0.17 ⁶	17 ⁶	99.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	17
↑temperature	0.12 ⁶	6 ⁶	49.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	17
↑salinity	4.3	20.4	3.7	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	18
Photoperiod short to long	1.4	2.4	0.7	<i>P. seriata</i>	19
Bacteria ⁷	0.03	0.52	16.3	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	20
Bacteria ⁷	0.17	3.27	18.2	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	20
Bacteria ⁷	0.04	0.32	7.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	20
Bacteria ⁷	0.01	0.38	37.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	20
Bacteria ⁷	0.88	8.23	8.35	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	20
↓Cell size	3.6	0.4	-0.9	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	4
↓Cell size	2.4	0.05	-1.0	<i>P. multiseriis</i>	4

*For calculation purposes set at the detection limit, **Below detection limits; ¹*Calanus hyperboreus*; ²*Calanus finmarchicus*; ³*Calanus glacialis*; ⁴*Calanus copepodites*; ⁵*Calanus copepodamides*; ⁶Estimated from the publication; ⁷Comparing axenic with non-axenic.

ture and that these cells may end up as being non-toxic (see refs in [1]). This decrease in toxin content over time has been related to a simultaneous decrease in cell size [4], as *Pseudo-nitzschia* cells, like other vegetative cells of diatoms, decrease in cell size with time and thus contain less toxin per cell. This hypothesis has been supported by observations of *P. cuspidata* of which some (but not all) of the large cells after sexual reproduction are more toxic than the smaller parent cells [5]. Another explanation for the decrease in toxin content over time is related to bacteria. A correlation between decreases in *Pseudo-nitzschia* toxin content and simultaneous changes over time in bacterial communities in *Pseudo-nitzschia* cultures has been hypothesized. Because some bacteria have been shown to promote DA production whereas others degrade DA, changes in bacterial communities might potentially be an explanation [6]. Changes in bacterial communities over time have been observed in some studies, but not others [7, 8].

In recent studies on interactions between copepods and *Pseudo-nitzschia*, grazing copepods (like *Calanus* species) have been shown to trigger an increase in toxin production [3, 9-11]. We hypothesize that the reason for a decrease in DA production over time in laboratory cultures might be related to a lack of grazers in laboratory cultures. When exposed to grazing copepods, toxin production has been shown to increase up

to 130 times, depending on exposure time (12 hours to 10 days) as well as concentration and species of copepod (Table 1, 2-5). One can easily imagine that the lack of such a potent toxin-trigger will have an effect. When establishing clonal cultures in the laboratory, single cells are removed from the natural environment and kept in pure cultures without exposure to grazers. The lack of the triggering factor that grazers exercise thus results in a continuous decrease in toxin production.

Toxin-inducing factors

A lack of copepod grazers may also explain why field data on cellular toxin content shows higher toxin levels than laboratory cultures of the same species from the same area [5]. But several other factors also influence production of DA. A preliminary comparison of some of the factors affecting DA production shows that toxin production may increase more than 100 times due to copepod grazing or depletion of phosphate and silicate, whereas presence of bacteria, salinity increase or pH increase showed a smaller degree of induction (See Table 1). This is not an exhaustive comparison and does not include the rate of toxin induction as the time of incubation was not available for many of the experiments, but may nonetheless give an indication of the importance of some of the factors affecting DA-production.

Apart from increasing toxin production in already toxic species/strains, presence of grazers may even induce toxin production in species previously considered non-toxic, as shown for *P. obtusa* [3]. It is therefore relevant to consider that all *Pseudo-nitzschia* species might have the potential to produce DA, given the appropriate triggering conditions. The results mentioned above illustrate the importance of considering different chemical, physical as well as biological factors when predicting and modelling toxicity of *Pseudo-nitzschia* in the field.

References:

1. Lundholm 2017. Diatoms. In <http://www.marinespecies.org/hab/>
2. Lelong A et al 2012. *Phycologia* 51: 168-216
3. Harðardóttir et al 2015. *Mar Drugs* 13: 3809-3835
4. Mafra LL Jr et al 2009. *Aquat Biol* 6: 201-212
5. Lundholm N et al 2012. *J Phycol* 48: 436-454
6. Stewart JE 2008. *Aquat Microb Ecol* 50: 135-144
7. Sapp et al 2007. *Microb Ecol* 53: 683-699
8. Guannel ML et al 2011. *Aquat Biol* 64: 117-133
9. Tammilehto A et al 2015. *Aquat Toxicol* 159: 52-61
10. Leandro LF et al 2010. *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol* 382: 88-95
11. Miesner A K et al 2016. *J Plankton Res* 38: 564-574
12. Sun J et al 2011. *Limnol Oceanogr* 56: 829-840
13. Trimborn S et al 2008. *Physiol Plant* 133: 92-105
14. Fehling J et al 2004. *J Phycol* 40: 622-630
15. Pan YL et al 1996. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 131: 225-233
16. Pan YL et al 1996. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 13: 235-243
17. Lewis NI 1993. In: Smayda TJ & Y Shimizu (eds) *Toxic Phytoplankton Blooms in the Sea*. Elsevier Science Publishers pp 601-606
18. Doucette GJ et al 2009. *Harmful Algae* 8: 880-888
19. Fehling J et al 2005. *Harmful Algae* 4: 763-769
20. Bates S et al 1995. *Nat Toxins* 3: 428-435

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Ecology of *Alexandrium* spp. in the Strait of Georgia, British Columbia, Canada 2015

Fig. 1 Citizen Science sampling stations in the Strait of Georgia, Canada in 2015.

Fig. 2. Citizen Science sampling areas in the Strait of Georgia, Canada in 2015.

Coastal waters of British Columbia (BC), Canada have one of the longest documented histories of Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) in the world [1, 2]. A monitoring program for the presence of toxins in shellfish was established in the 1940s [3]. Since then, PSP closures have been occurring every year. In the Strait of Georgia, PSP is primarily caused by the genus *Alexandrium*. Little is known about *Alexandrium* spp. distribution and its environmental preferences in the Strait of Georgia. Currently, the government does not have a harmful algae monitoring program in BC.

The Citizen Science Program was initiated in 2015 by the Pacific Salmon

Foundation, the Department of Fisheries and Oceans Canada, and Ocean Networks Canada. The purpose of the program is to monitor the Strait of Georgia and provide data at a spatial and temporal scale not possible before. Properties/samples that are being measured/collected include phytoplankton, zooplankton, temperature, salinity, density, dissolved nutrients, fluorescence, oxygen, and turbidity. Sampling for phytoplankton is performed at approximately 80 sites (Figs. 1, 2) throughout the Strait every two weeks from February to October. At each site phytoplankton samples are collected from the surface (0 m). Among these 80 sites, there are ~

10 stations where additional samples at 5, 10, and 20 m are collected. Nutrients and environmental data are collected at ~30 sites. The majority of the data can be found at the Ocean Networks Canada and Strait of Georgia Data Centre websites – <http://www.oceannetworks.ca> and <http://www.sogdatacentre.ca>. Here we share observations on distribution, abundance, and environmental preferences of *Alexandrium* spp. in the Strait of Georgia.

In 2015, 1037 sea surface water samples were collected in the Strait of Georgia. Of these samples, 107 (10.3%) contained cells of *Alexandrium* spp. *Alexandrium* spp. were observed most frequently in Ladysmith and Cowichan Bay samples, while least frequently in Campbell River, Nanaimo, and Steveston (Table 1). It has to be noted, that the total number of samples collected in Ladysmith and Steveston in 2015 were very low (Ladysmith was an opportunistic area sampled by the Stz'uminus First Nations when possible and Steveston area was added to the Citizen Science Program half way through the sampling season). Thus, the frequency of occurrence in Ladysmith and Steveston is not as representative as in the rest of the areas, where sampling was done more systematically. As for the temporal distribution, cells of *Alexandrium* spp. were the most abundant in May – August samples (Table 1).

Cell densities. The majority of samples containing *Alexandrium* spp. showed low densities with only a few cells per mL (approximately 50% of the samples had ~ 1 cell mL⁻¹ and 25% had ~2 cells mL⁻¹). The remaining 25% of the samples had densities of 3-18 cells mL⁻¹ with all samples with densities > 8 cells mL⁻¹ (N=15) occurring in Ladysmith and Cowichan Bay samples. Temporal patterns in these two areas (with averaged per area *Alexandrium* spp. densities > 1 cell mL⁻¹) are illustrated in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

Temperature and salinity. There were 48 cases when temperature and salinity were recorded (at 0.5 m) along with phytoplankton samples containing at least 1 cell mL⁻¹ of *Alexandrium* spp. (at 0 m). *Alexandrium* spp. cells were observed in a wide range of temperatures from 9 to 22 °C and salinities from 20 to 31 ppt (Fig. 5). The highest densities of *Alexandrium* spp. (10-13 cells mL⁻¹, N=4) were observed in

Table 1. Number of water samples (N) collected by the Citizen Science Program, frequency of samples with *Alexandrium* spp. presence (Alex. +), and number of water samples with *Alexandrium* spp. cells present by month, Strait of Georgia 2015 (n/a - no samples were collected).

Area	Samples (N)	(% Alex. +)	Month						
			Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
Ladysmith	27	63	n/a	n/a	1	10	4	n/a	2
Cowichan Bay	149	26	1		10	n/a	18	6	4
Lund	128	13			3	6	5	1	1
Irvine Sechel	83	11	1		1		3	4	
Baynes sound	98	9		2	1	4		1	
Victoria	99	6				2	3	1	
Powell River	162	4	1		1	2		3	
Campbell River	144	2			1	2			
Nanaimo	107	2	1			1			
Steveston	40	0							

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of dissolved nutrients values ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) at 2 and 20 m when *Alexandrium* spp. cells were present at 0 m in 1 mL of the sample (N=20 samples)

	Nutrients at 0 m			Nutrients at 20 m		
	NO ₃ + NO ₂	SiO ₃	PO ₄	NO ₃ + NO ₂	SiO ₃	PO ₄
Min	0,03	11,30	0,24	10,70	8,97	1,31
Max	19,31	45,98	1,81	24,97	47,87	2,27
Mean	4,22	24,17	0,84	16,97	34,15	1,77
SE	1,18	2,25	0,09	1,13	2,16	0,07
Var	27,67	101,33	0,17	25,65	93,08	0,10

Fig. 3. Average density of *Alexandrium* spp. at the Ladysmith sites (N=5) from June to September, 2015

Fig. 4. Average density of *Alexandrium* spp. at the Cowichan Bay sites (N=13) from July to September, 2015

Fig. 5. Temperature and salinity values at 0.5 m when *Alexandrium* spp. cells were present at 0 m in 1 mL of the sample (N=48)

a range of 16-19 °C and 26-28 ppt.

Nutrients. There were only 20 cases when dissolved nutrient samples were collected (at 2 and 20 m) along with phytoplankton samples containing at least 1 cell mL⁻¹ of *Alexandrium* spp. (at 0 m) and where nutrient values were above zero within analytical uncertainty. Nutrient values varied dramatically (Table 3) and due to the small sample size, no clear pattern between nutrient values and *Alexandrium* spp. presence was established. An interesting observation was that out of these 20 cases, there were only 2 with high *Alexandrium* spp. density (~8 and ~10 cells mL⁻¹); the remaining 18 cases had 1-3 cells mL⁻¹ and in both of these cases, nitrate and nitrite values (at 2 m) were relatively high (7.44 and 6.7 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, respectively).

The year of 2015 was unusually warm due to El Niño. In the Strait of Georgia the majority of the total phytoplankton biomass was comprised of diatoms, while the dinoflagellate contribution was very low

and silicoflagellates and raphidophytes were almost absent (Pacific Salmon Foundation, internal data). Hence, data on *Alexandrium* spp. distribution, abundance and environmental preferences reported here are limited and represent the behaviour of such harmful algae in an unusual year. The most important observation of the *Alexandrium* spp. distribution in the Strait of Georgia in 2015 was that location and season were the most important factors in *Alexandrium* spp. presence and absence. The Citizen Science Program supported by PSF is continuing the collection and analysis of samples through 2016 and 2017. This anticipated 3 year continuation of data collection will be highly beneficial in understanding the local ecology of PSP-causing species.

Acknowledgments

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References

1. Vancouver G. 1798. In: Robinson GG & J Robinson (eds) Vol. 2, 4th book, chapter 2 (Paternoster-Row and J Edwards, London) pp 260-287
2. Fisheries and Oceans Canada 2017. Shellfish Contamination in the Pacific Region. <http://www.pac.dfo-mpo.gc.ca/fm-gp/contamination/index-eng.html>
3. Taylor FJR & PJ Harrison 2002. In: Taylor FJR & VM Trainer (eds) Harmful algal blooms in the PICES region of the North Pacific. PICES Rep. 23, pp 77-88

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A clarification of three unnamed raphidophytes previously described from British Columbia

An algal bloom implicated in the mass deaths of farmed salmon in Simoom Sound, BC, in early October 1990, was partly described in 1992 [1] and largely misdescribed in 2010 [2]. It was dominated by cold temperate raphidophytes, recorded, respectively as 'Raphidophytes 1 & 2', and *Chattonella* sp. and described in Waters et al [3] and Forbes & Waters [4]. The water temperature during the bloom was 13°C and the salinity 26ppt.

The *Chattonella* sp. grouping was a combination of two unrelated species, chiefly an unnamed dictyochophyte whose rapid change of form (see below) brings it into the genus *Vicicitus* as characterised by Chang et al [5] p. 409. The motile cells of *Vicicitus* sp. from this bloom were examined in a settling chamber using an inverted microscope. Most of the cells were globular, ~30-50 µm long and brownish to greenish gold in appearance. The chloroplasts were discoid, diameter 2.0-3.4 µm. Numer-

ous minute osmiophilic particles in the cell periphery were interspersed with small vesicles. The cell recreated in Fig. 1 glided forward slowly, with the leading flagellum held straight, vibrating at high speed, while the other flagellum lashed around from time to time. The flagella arose together from a circular, conical, anterior depression that came into view when the cell turned downwards. After a while the cell flattened and suddenly became amoeboid, with several pseudopodia of different widths (see description in ([5] p. 408). These spread outwards fast, a long way, stopped briefly and returned slowly, all within 30 seconds (see [5] p. 408). This activity was repeated for at least 5 minutes most probably in an apparent attempt to find other cells (see [5] p. 408), but they were too far away and the amoeboid one eventually became inactive. The chloroplasts had single pyrenoids that showed up in the Lugol-fixed amoeboid cell in Fig. 2 #3. An elon-

gated motile cell with very similar chloroplasts and the oval Lugol-fixed cell in Fig. 2 #3 were probably equivalent to the long cells formed by *V. globosus* in stationary growth (see [5] Figs. 7 & 8).

Raphidophyte 2 [3] (Fig. 2 #2), a bloom-forming species [4], may belong to the same genus as Raphidophyte 1 (below). A basic ventral view of a motile cell in Waters et al [3] is reproduced here as Fig. 3. Its jagged outline is due to its protruding extrusomes. The cells are dorsoventrally narrow, concave ventrally, convex dorsally, 8-13 µm long, 6-10 µm wide, with 4-6 yellow-brown discoid chloroplasts. The normal swimming action is a swivelling glide directed by the curving of the anterior flagellum.

Raphidophyte 1 [2]/F.J.R. Taylor's Undescribed chloromonad [6] is M.R. Droop's fragile, golden-brown Flagellate X [7]. Droop's species germinated at a water temperature of 6°C and formed a bloom at 7°C in upper Loch Striven, Argyll, Scotland, in early May 1979 [7]. It is described as follows: "Examination of live material (figure 5) suggested it to be a chloromonad related to *Vacuolaria* and *Gonyostomum*. It seemed especially similar to *Olisthodiscus*" (Droop et al [7]). The drawings in Droop's Fig. 5 are

Fig. 1. *Vicicitus* sp. Motile cell, 47 µm long, 55 µm wide.

Fig. 2. Simplified depictions of six marine flagellates fixed with acid Lugol's solution. Scale bar 10 µm. #1: Raphidophyte 1 from the 1990 bloom; #2: Raphidophyte 2 from the 1990 bloom and ocean surface waters; #3: *Vicicitus* sp. from the 1990 bloom; #6 *H. akashiwo*: from the 1990 bloom.

Fig. 3. *Raphidophyte 2* from a culture in 1974. Motile cell, ventral view 11.5 μm long.

Fig. 4. Flagellate X from Droop 1979. Cell size about 20 μm . #1 Ventral face, anterior end down; note the thin and overlapping chloroplasts. #2 The same cell under stress, its ejected extrusomes apparently unfilled. #3 A cell shrunk by the apparent transfer of mucilage to the extrusomes, which have released it and dispersed (#1-3 captions are interpretations from the author).

reproduced here at a smaller size (Fig. 4) and are interpreted (in the figure caption) by the author.

Photographs of motile cells under stress received from Nicky Haigh (*Microthalassia*) (not shown here) reveal that the extrusomes are flexible and not the impediment to motility that they appear to be in Fig. 4 #2. They are more evenly distributed and more uniform in width except for constricted distal ends. Nicky's cells have a tubular posterior invagination on their ventral side and a corresponding shallow recess on their dorsal, which may explain why the cells in the 1990 bloom split open in the fixative (Fig. 2 #1). Those cells were growing fast when they were col-

lected. Slow-growing cells have round chloroplasts in Lugol's-fixed material, where they can resemble *Heterosigma akashiwo* (Fig. 2 #6). Although the two species have different water temperature requirements, they can both be present at high concentrations in the same bloom in BC coastal waters [2,4].

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References

1. Waters R 1992. *Aquaculture Association of BC Newsletter* 8 (2): 6-10, out of print

2. Waters RE 2010. *Harmful Algae News* 41:3-5
3. Waters RE et al 1992. *Can Tech Rep Hydrogr Ocean Sci* 137, 59 pp
4. Forbes JR & RE Waters 1993. *Can Data Rep Hydrogr Ocean Sci* 117 Vol 1: 1979-1984, 212 pp Vol 2: 1985-1989, 247 pp
5. Chang FH et al 2012. *Phycologia* 51): 403-420
6. Taylor FJR, Haigh R & TF Sutherland 1991. In: Forbes JR (ed) 1991. *Can Tech Rep Hydrogr Ocean Sci* 135:23-28
7. Droop MR et al 1979. In: Tett P (ed) 1980. *Scottish Mar Biol Assoc Internal Report* 25: 88-97

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IOC-IAEA guide for designing and implementing a plan to monitor toxin-producing microalgae

The IOC and IAEA are proud to announce the publication of IOC Manuals & Guides no 59

This manual is intended as an introduction to basic analytical techniques that can be applied when designing a standard sampling protocol for both planktonic and benthic microalgae (and asso-

ciated environmental conditions) and vectors of biotoxins (shellfish and fish). This standardization of methods will enable more robust data comparisons between countries and will yield improved risk assessments of potentially toxic HABs events. <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0021/002145/214510e.pdf>

Autumnal algal bloom succession in northern coasts of Gulf of Oman

Fig. 1. Map of the study area

The composition of harmful algal blooms is determined by the diversity and abundance of different species present. Temporal fluctuations in phytoplankton populations can lead to a succession of different species dominating the phytoplankton community. Typically, phytoplankton blooms dominated by small and fast growing diatoms is followed by slow-growing larger diatoms which in turn is followed by the occurrence of large dinoflagellates [1]. Bloom succession is mainly controlled by physical factors, nutrient availability, mixotrophy and competition/predation [2]. The diversity within temporal phytoplankton bloom succession is discussed on the basis of decadal [3], annual [4], or seasonal [5] changes in species composition. Finer-scale changes (e.g. diurnal) may also occur [6]. The first phytoplankton bloom report in Gulf of Oman dates back to 1970s [7]. Since then, there have been regular reports of red tide incidents within the Gulf area which peaked in 2009 with more than 12 events in a single year [7]. To assess the autumnal succession of algal blooms on the northern coasts of Gulf of Oman, phytoplankton sampling was conducted irregularly (i.e. based on incidence of water discoloration) along Chabahar coasts (Fig. 1). Bloom species were identified and counted using light microscopy. The first detectable discoloration occurred on 26 October 2016 with a dominance of *Alexandrium* sp. (Table 1). This event was followed by an extensive bloom of *Prorocentrum* sp that lasted three days. This bloom resulted in the failure of a desalination plant in the city as a result of clogging.

Next, an outbreak of *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* covered nearly the whole Chabahar Bay (i.e. from Ramin coast to Chabahar Bay). Cell densities at the time of the bloom exceeded 1.5×10^6 cells L^{-1} (Table 1). Approximately 20 days later, a green tide reported by local fisherman, occurred along almost the whole coast.

Fine examination of water samples indicated predominance of green *Noctiluca scintillans* (Fig. 2) in surface waters (Table 1). Finally, a dense bloom of *Mesodinium rubrum* (Fig. 2) occurred on 4th December 2016. To our knowledge this is the first report of *Mesodinium rubrum* blooms in the Gulf of Oman. During the course of these algal blooms, the maximum pH, temperature and dissolved oxygen coincided with the *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* bloom, while maximum salinity was recorded at the time of the *Noctiluca scintillans* bloom (Table 1). Recent evidence suggests that dinoflagellates are replacing diatoms (e.g. *Lauderia punctata*, *Chaetoceros* spp., *Guinardia striata* and *Thalassiosira* spp.) in the Gulf of Oman and becoming dominant the HAB species [8]. In this case, controlling future algal blooms may become more difficult in the region since dinoflagellate blooms are less predictable and more ephemeral compared to diatom blooms [9].

Fig. 2. Top, green tide of *Noctiluca* and bottom, bloom of *Mesodinium rubrum* in Chabahar, Gulf of Oman, autumn 2016.

Table 1. Maximal mean density of the observed bloom species and physical-chemical properties of the near-shore waters during autumnal algal blooms in the northern Gulf of Oman

Date	Species/ Genus	Mean density maxima ($\times 10^6$)	Temperature	Salinity	pH	DO (mg/L)
26 October 2016	<i>Alexandrium</i> sp.	1.5	24.4	36.3	8.10	8.30
04 November 2016	<i>Prorocentrum</i> sp.	1.53	25.5	37.8	8.00	5.10
09 November 2016	<i>Cochlodinium polykrikoides</i>	1.7	27.0	36.4	8.40	11.20
29 November 2016	<i>Noctiluca scintillans</i>	0.007	25.1	36.6	8.14	6.58
03 December 2016	<i>Mesodinium</i> sp.	3.1	25.5	36.6	8.25	9.50

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References

- Margalef R 1958. In: Buzzati-Traverso AA (eds) *Perspective in marine biology* (University of California Press, Berkeley) pp 323-349
- Jeong HJ et al 2015. *Harmful Algae* 47: 97-115
- Mudie PJ et al 2002. *Palaeogeogr Palaeoclimatol Palaeoecol* 180(1): 159-186
- Viquez R & PE Hargraves 1995. *Bull Mar Sci* 57(2): 467-475
- Anderson DM & K Rengefors 2006. *Limnol Oceanogr* 51(2): 860-873
- Suzuki K et al 1997. *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol* 214(1): 1-17
- Al-Gheilani HM et al 2011. *J Agri Mar Sci* 16:23-33
- Harrison PJ et al 2017. *Mar Pollut Bull* 114(1): 25-34
- Smayda TJ & CS Reynolds 2003. *J Sea Res* 49(2): 95-106.

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6th Congress of the International Society for Applied Phycology (ISAP)

The poster features a central illustration of a laboratory flask containing a vibrant, multi-colored algal bloom (green, yellow, orange, red, blue) with various microscopic organisms and chemical structures. To the right, the text reads: "6TH CONGRESS OF THE INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY FOR APPLIED PHYCOLOGY", "18TH TO 23RD JUNE 2017", "LA CITÉ NANTES EVENTS CENTER NANTES FRANCE", and "HTTPS://ISAP2017.SCIENCESCONF.ORG". Logos for the International Society for Applied Phycology (ISAP) and ISAP NANTES 2017 are in the top right. At the bottom, logos for GEPEA (UMR CNRS 6144), UNIVERSITÉ DE NANTES, and BIOTECHNOLOGIES GREENSEA (Marine Bioactives) are displayed.

Over 400 scientists and producers of micro- and macro-algal products are expected to meet during the 6th Congress of the International Society for

Applied Phycology in Nantes from the 18-23 June 2017. To join them see the website for details: <https://isap2017.sciencesconf.org/>

Nodularin accumulation in New Zealand shortfin eel from Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa

Fig. 1. Map showing Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa, the eel gaffing site and the location of the lake in New Zealand (inset).

Lake Forsyth is a small coastal lake on the Banks Peninsula in the Canterbury region of New Zealand; 7.8 km long and 1.3 km at its widest point (Fig. 1). The Māori name for the lake, *Te Roto o Wairewa*, means 'water lifted up' and in Māori legends Te Wairewa was the last lake to be dug out by Rākaihautū as he sculpted the lakes and mountains of the South Island of New Zealand. The lake is very important to the local Rūnanga (tribe) and has provided an important food source, both historically and at present. In early historic times Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa was an estuarine environment, however persistent deposition of gravel from nearby rivers eventually led to the closing of the estuary mouth. The closure and a significant increase in sediment flow into the lake over the last 150 years due to deforestation has, in part led to a decline in the lake's water quality [1] and since the early 1900s it has been described as eutrophic, suffering from persistent blooms of the cyanobacterium *Nodularia spumigena* (Fig. 2).

The water levels of Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa must be artificially controlled to mitigate the risk from land inundation. To do this, a channel was cut through the gravel to link the lake to the sea. Typically the shortest route was taken. The channels are temporary; quickly filled in due to the high-energy waves moving gravel along the shore plus the dominant drift of sediment down the coast from the braided rivers located to the north. The earliest recorded artificial opening of the lake was

in 1866 [2] and, from the 1940's onwards, openings have been carried out regularly. In 2008, the rūnanga attempted to create a permanent opening by constructing a 900 m canal and 300 m groyne at the eastern end of the beach against the cliffs. Although the end of this canal can become blocked, it is a more straightforward process to re-open it than creating a beach channel. The flow

rates of the canal are also considerably lower than that generated from a beach channel. This has an advantage of being able to control lake levels more effectively and the less turbulent flow-rate may assist in the recruitment of elvers (glass eels) during spring openings. There has been some improvement in water quality and lake ecology over this time (e.g., growth of macrophyte beds and resulting clear water within the beds), which may be attributed to better control of lake levels. However, the lake has had a recent downturn in 2016, with some of the most severe and prolonged cyanobacteria blooms reported to-date. As *Nodularia spumigena* commonly produces the hepatotoxin nodularin, farm stock deaths have been encountered along the shores of Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa. In 2016, 30 sheep were reported to have died after drinking from the lake, as well as several dogs belonging to nearby residents.

Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa is a valuable wetland ecosystem, providing homes for a variety of waterfowl and aquatic animals such as flounder, bullies, whitebait, banded kōkopu and eel (or tuna in Māori). Introduced fish species such as perch and brown trout can also be found in the lake. As nodularin has been shown to accumulate in aquatic animals [3-7], we investigated the accumulation of the toxin in shortfin eel (*Anguilla australis*) from the lake [8]. Shortfin eel are native to New Zealand, but are also found in south-eastern Australia and some Pacific islands. In many of New Zealand's freshwater

food webs they are the apex predator, and as opportunistic scavengers, they play an important role in recycling nutrients. They are primarily found in lowland lakes, estuaries and the lower reaches of rivers, and can reach a maximum size of approximately 3 kg and 1.1 m in length [9]. They are catadromous, and on reaching maturity (6-24 yrs for males, 10-34 yrs for females), the eels stop feeding and migrate up to three or four thousand kilometres over approximately four months to a deep water spawning ground somewhere off New Caledonia [10].

In New Zealand, tuna (eels) have huge customary and cultural significance to the indigenous Māori population. They are integral to their whakapapa (genealogies or stories which create a foundation of meaning for the people) and are an important mahinga kai (traditional food source). In recognition of the importance of eels to Māori, the New Zealand government set aside a number of waterways for eel fishing by only the local Māori people, including Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa. In autumn, migrating eels gather at the gravel bar separating the lake from the sea where small channels are dug into the gravel bar at the bottom of the lake (Fig.3A; Site indicated on Fig.1). As the eels gather in the channels, they are gaffed (speared) using a pole with a sharp hook on the end (Fig. 3B). Historically, up to several hundred eels were harvested per night when conditions were suitable. More recent studies suggest that shortfin eel populations in the lake are in a state of decline [11].

Because of the persistent cyanobacterial blooms and the human consumption of these eels, we assessed if nodularin accumulated in shortfin eels from Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa, and whether the concentrations would pose a risk to the health of humans who consume them [8]. Nodularin is heat-stable and thus not destroyed by cooking. With the help of the local rūnanga and others we collected migratory and feeding (non-migratory) shortfin eels, and analysed the liver and muscle tissue for nodularin content. Surface water samples were also collected to assess the concentration of *N. spumigena* and nodularin in the water. The samples were collected opportunistically between 2004 and 2014.

Fig. 2. *Nodularia spumigena* from Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa at 400× magnification (A) and blooms of the cyanobacterium at the lake in 2006 (B).

Fig. 3. Eel fishing channels at Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa (A) and members of the rūnanga of Wairewa catching eels in the channels by gaffing (B; photo provided by Jack Jacob).

The data from the water samples indicated that there was seasonal variation in concentrations of *N. spumigena* and nodularin, but that the severity of the blooms were decreasing over the study period [8]. Being able to maintain higher lake levels via the new canal may have contributed to these decreases in *N. spumigena* blooms. However, high concentrations of other phytoplankton (including cyanobacteria) remain persistent in the lake and it is still considered hypertrophic [12]. In December 2016, a statutory plan for reducing sediment and phosphorus inputs into Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa was announced and this may lead to further reductions in phytoplankton blooms in the lake.

In the eel samples, higher nodularin concentrations were observed in the liver of the eels than in the muscle tissue of the corresponding specimen. This was consistent with similar studies on nodularin accumulation in aquatic animals [4,13,14]. The highest nodularin concentrations detected in the eels from Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa (29 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ wet-weight in muscle tissue and 147 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ wet-weight in liver) [8] were within the same order of magnitude for those reported in aquatic organisms experiencing *N. spumigena* blooms (473 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ dry-weight in flounder muscle tis-

sue, 139 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ dry-weight in mussels and 399 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ dry-weight in flounder liver) [4,7,13]. Mulvenna et al. [15] suggested a guideline for safe human consumption of microcystin and/or nodularin in fish of 24 $\mu\text{g toxin kg}^{-1}$ (for a 2-16 year age group). The concentrations in the muscle of shortfin eels from Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa exceeded this suggested safe human consumption guideline only on one occasion (29 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ wet weight). Concentrations detected in the liver exceeded the suggested value in 36% of samples analysed. Fortunately, local Rūnanga (who are the main consumers of the eels) currently remove the liver prior to consumption, and removal of the gut/organs would be recommended for anyone consuming aquatic foodstuffs from bloom-affected waters.

Shortfin eels from Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa are an important mahinga kai source for the local rūnanga of Wairewa and are a taonga species (treasured species) around New Zealand. Our study suggested that, provided the liver (and other intestinal organs) are removed, the risk of adverse effects to human health from consumption of the eels was low [8]. The data from our study also indicated that the concentrations of nodularin in the water column impacted on the levels detected in the

eels. Therefore, the assumption of low human health risk may need to be revisited now that intense and prolonged blooms have returned to Lake Forsyth/Te Wairewa. While the risk to humans may be considered low, the consequences of nodularin exposure on the eels remains unknown. We suggest that better understanding of these effects and improving knowledge on the transport of nodularin through trophic levels should be a priority for future research in this area.

References

1. Woodward CA & J Shulmeister 2005. *J Paleolimnol* 34: 481-501
2. Jacobson WEM 1940. *Akaroa and Banks Peninsula: 1840-1940. Akaroa Mail*
3. Karjalainen M et al 2003. *Environ Toxicol* 18: 52-60
4. Mazur-Marzec H et al 2007. *Environ Toxicol* 22: 101-111
5. Sipiä VO et al 2002. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf* 53: 305-311
6. Sipiä VO et al 2004. *Environ Toxicol Chem* 23: 1256-1260
7. Sipiä VO et al 2006. *Environ Toxicol Chem* 25: 2834-2839
8. Dolamore B et al 2016. *N Z J Mar Fresh DOI:10.1080/00288330.2016.1236738*
9. Todd PR 1980. *N Z J Mar Fresh* 14: 283-293
10. Todd PR 1981. *N Z J Mar Fresh* 15: 225-235
11. Jellyman DJ & I Cranwell I 2007. *The status of eel stocks in Wairewa (Lake Forsyth). New Zealand Fisheries Assessment Report 2007/11; New Zealand Ministry of Fisheries, p 41*
12. Schallenberg M & LA Schallenberg 2013. *Lake Forsyth/Wairewa: A literature review. Report No R13/106; Environment Canterbury Technical Report prepared by Hydrosphere Research Ltd, p 33*
13. Sipiä VO et al 2001. *Environ Toxicol* 16: 330-336
14. Wood SA et al 2012. *Harmful Algae* 20: 175-179
15. Mulvenna V et al 2012. *Int J Env Res Public Health* 9: 807-820

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The Scottish Coastal Observatory

Scotland's coastal environment is subject to inherent variability resulting from short term processes such as tides and weather, the seasonal cycle, multi-annual cycles such as the North Atlantic Oscillation and larger scale influences such as climate change and ocean acidification. In order to understand how these processes impact the ecosystem goods and services produced in Scottish coastal waters, long term time series of data are needed.

Scientists in Marine Scotland Science (MSS), along with a small group of voluntary citizen-scientists, have been monitoring the physics, chemistry and biology at multiple sites in Scotland's coastal waters since 1997. Sustained time series of ecological data such as these are scarce and interest in this data

set is growing at both a national and international level, both for assessments of the status and health of our marine ecosystems as well as for input to blueskies research, such as project proposals and studentships.

MSS has recently re-badged this monitoring programme as the Scottish Coastal Observatory (SCOs). As a first step to improve information and the availability of data from this programme, a three part report [1] has been compiled to provide a basic description of the seasonality and variability of the main parameters examined between 1997 and 2013. These include temperature, salinity, nutrients, carbonate chemistry, chlorophyll *a*, algal toxins measured using passive sampling, phytoplankton and zooplank-

ton. A chapter summarising supportive meteorological (air temperature, frost, sunshine) and river flow data has also been included. The data used in this report are available on request with a summary of monthly means of the parameters described in the report available for download [2].

HAB highlights include a description of the regional and interannual variation of shellfish toxin producing phytoplankton genera at the SCOs monitoring sites. A slight increase in the abundance of *Alexandrium* was observed at monitoring sites on the west coast towards the end of the period covered by the report. The diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia* was present in nearly every phytoplankton sample analysed but in contrast to the other SCOs monitoring sites is not a component of the spring bloom diatom community at the monitoring site at Scalloway in the Shetland Islands. *Dinophysis* cell densities showed the most variability between sites and years with cell densities increasing in at the monitoring site at Millport in the Clyde, and decreasing at Scapa Bay in Orkney during the monitoring period covered by [1]. Passive sampling methods revealed the increased detection of the algal toxin, azaspiracid, in the water column during winter months.

Monitoring at the SCOs sites is ongoing. Data from SCOs is a national resource and its value increases the more it is used. If you would like to find out more about SCOs or use these data, please email Scobs@gov.scot.

References

1. Bresnan E et al 2016. *Scottish Marine and Freshwater Science Report Vol 7 No 26*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.7489/1881-1>
2. *Marine Scotland Science 2016*. doi: 10.7489/1761-1.

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The “RedFAN” network: a working group to deal with HABs in Mexico

In October 2014 the network RedFAN (from the acronym in Spanish: “Red temática sobre Florecimientos Algales Nocivos”) was created with the financial support of the Mexican National Council of Science and Technology (CONACyT). This network integrates the academic community (researchers and students), the public health, production and government sectors interested in problems related to harmful algal blooms in the coastal and offshore marine environments. The goal of RedFAN is to contribute to the understanding of HABs, their impact on the public health and ecosystems and, under an interdisciplinary approach, to propose mitigation actions and management plans for HABs in Mexico. This network looks for the integration of different social sectors affected by HAB phenomena to consolidate collaboration and to elaborate and implement a National Plan to respond to the increasing problem of the presence of HABs and their impacts in Mexico.

The organization of RedFAN started in 2014 with a small group of colleagues

working on diverse aspects of harmful blooms in Mexico. In one of the working sessions, Juan Blanco (CIMA, Spain) shared his experience and made recommendations. A working plan was developed and five programs were created focused on the study of HABs: ecology, autecology, toxinology, taxonomy, mitigation, and socioeconomic impacts. An academic technical committee leads the actions and operation of the network.

Currently RedFAN has 120 members: 98% belong to the academic sector, i.e. researchers and students from Universities and research centers. Only 2% of the membership is from public health departments and the private sector. Most members represent institutions situated in Mexican coastal states. Participants of interior states are practically missing and only members from Mexico City (capital of the Country) form part of the network.

Activities began formally in June 2015 with a workshop on HAB in shelf waters, held in Cuernavaca, Morelos. It was followed by a workshop on emerging toxins held in La Paz, Baja California

Sur in November, with Andrew Turner (CEFAS, UK) as a special guest. A last workshop on science dissemination was held in Ensenada, Baja California in December of the same year. In addition to these workshops, an introductory course on the study of HABs was created and has been offered to pre and post graduate students. This course provides an introductory overview of different aspects of HABs and presents the state of knowledge about them in Mexico. The course has been already held in Ensenada, Baja California in September 2015 and in La Paz, Baja California Sur in 2016. Professors from different institutes and expertise, all of them RedFAN members, participated in the course. Students (around 20), most of them supported by RedFAN, were from different regions of Mexico and from Central and South America (Panama and Peru).

In 2016 different actions for the internationalization of RedFAN were undertaken. The RedFAN network supported a research stay of Allan Cembella AWI, Germany) in La Paz, B.C.S., Mexico, where he collaborated with colleagues and students of two research centers: IPN-CICIMAR and CIBNOR.

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Fig. 1. Web page of the Mexican Network RedFAN (<http://redfan.cicese.mx>)

Caribbean Ciguatera Experts Discuss a Risk Management System for the IOCARIBE Region

Over the past three decades the incidence of ciguatera has increased in the Caribbean countries by about 32% [1]. Despite the evidence of toxic events and their potential consequences on public health, fisheries and tourism, very few countries in the region have developed management plans to address this issue. To analyze the situation, IOCARIBE, ANCA and the CCO (Colombian Ocean Commission), convened a workshop of Caribbean experts.

The objective of the meeting, held on 17th and 18th August, 2016 at INVEMAR (Santa Marta, Colombia), was to propose a risk management system for the Greater Caribbean concerning HAB events, with a particular focus on Ciguatera Fish Poisoning.

Representatives from many institutions – the General Maritime Director, the National Navy of Colombia, the Ministry of Health and Social Protection, the National Institute of Health, Health Secretariats of Sucre, San Andres Island, Antioquia and Magdalena, the National Authority for Aquaculture and Fisheries, INVEMAR, National University of Colombia, and the Colombian Commission of the Ocean - attended the workshop. In addition, there were participants from Cuba (National Toxicology Center of Cuba and Fisheries Research Center) and Panama (University of

Panama and the Panamanian Maritime Authority).

During the workshop, the status of ciguatera in the IOCARIBE region was discussed, with particular emphasis on medical issues. Cuba, Colombia and Panama, presented national reports, showing some similar problems and the mechanisms developed to deal with ciguatera problems in each country. The experts analyzed the main needs in the region in terms of knowledge, resources and legislation.

Resulting from the meeting was a recognition by the experts of the need for a regional risk management system for the Greater Caribbean to deal with ciguatera fish poisoning. This system should incorporate the largest number of IOC Member States impacted, coordinate actions with other regional initiatives and projects and optimize the existing infrastructure in the region.

The IOC-ANCA group, supported by IOCARIBE, should continue to serve as a coordination mechanism to strengthen this system. In this respect participants agreed upon specific commitments, such as:

- Preparation of guidelines for research and capacity building.
- Summarize the status of Ciguatera in each country.
- Assess the gaps, requirements, con-

straints, and bottle-necks of the system.

To contribute to the global IOC strategy on Ciguatera and reduce vulnerability through the generation of knowledge about the biology, ecology, physiology and toxicity of benthic microalgae present in marine ecosystems, the experts proposed to develop a joint macro-regional plan with WESTPAC (ANCA-WESTPAC).

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to IOCARIBE, Ministry of Health and Social Protection, CCO and INVEMAR, for financial and technical support for the meeting.

References

1. Celis JS & JE Mancera-Pineda 2015. *Biol Invest Mar Cost* 44(1): 7-32

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Fig. 1. Workshop of Caribbean Experts on Ciguatera: Participants attending the IOCARIBE-ANCA-CCO Workshop on Ciguatera at INVEMAR (Santa Marta, Colombia), 17-18 August 2016

IOC/WESTPAC Scientists Shape the Future of Regional HAB Research

More than twenty experts from countries in the Western Pacific gathered in Nha Trang, Vietnam, 19-22 December 2016 to foster cooperation and define research priorities for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in the region (Fig. 1).

The East and Southeast Asian countries in the Western Pacific are populated by more than 3 billion people whose activities have been inextricably linked to ocean, with large impacts on the surrounding coastal waters and marine ecosystems.

Primarily associated with escalating human activities, coastal aquaculture, nutrient inputs and water quality degradation in coastal systems are expected to increase in many areas in the region. According to recent reports, the occurrence of HABs and their social-economic impacts seem to be increasing in the

WESTPAC area. Therefore, it is essential for HAB scientists in the region to provide scientific input, transfer of technology, and bridge the gap between science and management in order to better assist countries in mitigating the negative impacts of HABs.

The regional workshop entitled “The Development of a Research Strategy for Harmful Algal Blooms: what we know, and what we do not know on HABs”, was initiated by the UNESCO/IOC Sub-Commission for the Western Pacific (WESTPAC), and kindly hosted by the Institute of Oceanography, Vietnam. The workshop was structured around three objectives:

1) to review current knowledge on HAB; 2) to identify scientific problems/questions/gaps, and 3) to develop a research strategy for HAB sciences in the region.

Following a series of institutional and national reports on current status and issues on HABs, scientific reviews were provided by some leading scientists to cover various aspects of HAB science in the region, including: (1) the biology and ecophysiology of HABs species (taxonomy, phylogeny and geographical distribution, bloom dynamics); (2) marine biotoxins (responsible species and their toxins, and fate of toxins in ecosystems); (3) fish kills mechanisms (causative mechanisms, including factors related to harmful substances and environment) and (4) socio-economic aspects of HAB outbreaks (economic losses, preventive measures and management) (Fig. 2).

Throughout the four-day workshop, all participants demonstrated their passion for closer cooperation among institutions and countries in the region. Lively discussions took place about the need for a regional research strategy with a view to addressing national and/or regional specific HABs and synergiz-

Fig. 1. Participants of the WESTPAC-HAB Workshop at the Institute of Oceanography, Nha Trang, Vietnam, 19-22 December 2016

Fig. 2. Talk on management and socio-economy of HABs by Dr. Kazumi Wakita.

Fig. 3. Prof. Gires Usup, IPHAB Chair, and Dr. Po Teen Lim, GlobalHAB SSC member, (first and second from left).

ing the ongoing HAB research and capacity building efforts at these levels. Dr. Po Teen Lim presented the science and implementation plans of the IOC-SCOR sponsored new GlobalHAB research program (Fig. 3). It was widely recognized that national and regional efforts are complementary to global efforts, which form a strong and essential basis to achieve the global objectives of HAB science. The workshop further identified the importance of multidisciplinary work to clarify bloom forming mechanisms, fish stress and fish mortalities and shellfish toxin accumulation (including fate of toxins in shellfish and why shellfish do not depurate toxins).

After the workshop, continued efforts are ongoing to develop a draft strategy and associated outreach materials. The draft will be distributed for further inputs during the 10th WEST-PAC International Scientific Conference, 17-20 April 2017, in Qingdao, China to encourage participation of HAB scientists in the region, and to strengthen networking and involvement of HABs researchers in both regional and international programs.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Dr. Dao Viet Ha (Vice Director, Institute of Oceanography, Nha Trang, Vietnam) for hosting the event and heartfelt hospitality provided during the workshop.

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IOC-SCOR GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee Meeting

The GlobalHAB programme was launched in January 2016, with financial support from the U.S. National Science Foundation (through SCOR) and from IOC. During this first year, the Scientific Steering Committee of GlobalHAB elaborated the draft of the Science and Implementation Plan of the programme. This document was based on suggestions from the international HAB community participating in the Open Science Meeting in Paris, April 2013, at the sunset of the former program GEOHAB. The draft was also enriched by many other contributions during the first year of the programme and subsequent inputs at the International Conference on Harmful Algae in Florianópolis, Brazil (October, 2016) and submitted to external revision.

The GlobalHAB SSC members will hold their second meeting in Naples, Italy, from 28 to 30 March 2017. The objectives of this meeting will be to finish edition of the revised Science and Implementation Plan. This document constitutes an addendum to the GEOHAB Science Plan. An analysis of the activities that can be implemented at short (1-2 years) and longer (until 2025) term, will also be conducted. The information will be soon available at the new webpage www.globalhab.info.

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ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics

The ICES-IOC WGHABD will meet on 25 - 28 April 2017, at the Finnish Environment Institute, Helsinki, Finland. Terms of reference to be addressed include production of a status report about harmful algal events in the ICES area, national reports, new findings and the ecology of *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* and cyanobacteria from the Baltic.

For more information, contact the WGHABD Chair at: E.Bresnan@marlab.ac.uk

13th Session of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms

The thirteenth Session of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IOC-IPHAB) will be held from 3 to 5 of May 2017 at the IOC headquarters in Paris, France. Detailed information on the agenda, list of participants and working documents will be available at: <http://hab.ioc-unesco.org/> (Upcoming Events).

By 1st April 2017, Member States should send detail of their delegation, comments on the draft provisional agenda, name of candidates to chair discussion panels, and nominate candidates for the post of Chair and Vice-chair of IPHAB. Member States which never participated in IPHAB sessions are invited to do so and to send a letter of interest for the programme together with the detail of their delegation to the session of its intergovernmental body.

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In memory of Paul Harrison

With great sorrow, we learned of the recent unexpected passing of our colleague, mentor and friend Paul J. Harrison. Among his many contributions, Paul was a founding member of the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) working Group 137 “SCOR WG 137 “ Global Patterns of Phytoplankton Dynamics in Coastal Ecosystems: Comparative Analysis of Time Series Observations” and the recently-formed IOC Working Group to “Investigate Climate Change and Global Trends of Phytoplankton in the Oceans” (IOC WG TrendsPO). Few people have had a larger impact on the oceanographic community than Paul. He was exceptional through his contributions as a scientist, and his ability to motivate others. Paul had a rich life that included a deep commitment to family, and the people he worked with. He also loved to share his excitement and knowledge of the oceans and never missed an opportunity to include family when possible. He was doing both this past December, giving natural history lectures to passengers on a Caribbean cruise, accompanied by members of his family. Unexpectedly, he became very ill while on board and passed away due to complications associated with influenza.

Paul grew up on a 300-acre farm and attended a one-room schoolhouse near the town of Uxbridge, northeast of Toronto. He had a passion for plants, and after completing a Bachelor’s degree at the University of Toronto, he went on to do a Master’s degree in plant ecology at the University of Guelph. While attending university in Toronto, he met Victoria; they were soon married and over the next 51 years embarked on many adventures together. The first big adventure was after Paul graduated from the University of Guelph. They signed up with CUSO (Canadian University Students Overseas) and headed off to Ghana on a two-year teaching contract. They used this opportunity to travel the Nile, climbed Mount Kilimanjaro and travel throughout East and West Africa. It was also here that they charted a course for the future that included pursuing a PhD in oceanography with Dick Dugdale at the University of Washington.

*Paul and Victoria Harrison.
Photo from Rachel Harrison*

Paul entered graduate school in 1967 and was soon interrogating phytoplankton and exploring their physiological response to varying nutrient supplies. This work led to a series of seminal papers on the nutrient physiology of diatoms and was the stimulus that led Paul to begin his lifelong pursuit of understanding phytoplankton growth, their population dynamics and their central role in ocean ecosystems.

Most of Paul’s career was at the University of British Columbia, where he began a faculty position in the Institute of Oceanography and the Department of Botany in 1975. He rapidly built an internationally recognized program in biological oceanography that attracted trainees from far and wide. Two of us (Curtis Suttle and Kedong Yin) were among the early students in Paul’s lab, but there were many others in those beginning days, including Dave Turpin (President of the University of Alberta), Charlie Trick (University of Western Ontario), Neil Price (McGill University), Peter Thompson and John Parslow (CSIRO, Tasmania), Bill Cochlan (University of San Francisco), Greg Doucette (NOAA), Lee Jackson (University of Calgary) and Maurice Lévassieur (Laval University); others that went on to productive non-academic careers ranging from medicine to environmental consulting. The students and post-docs kept coming to learn from the guru of phytoplankton, and over the years 45 graduate students, 15 postdoctoral scholars and countless undergraduates trained with him. Many of these peo-

ple, too many to list here, went on to be leaders in academia, government and industry. Paul never stopped mentoring and inspiring those around him. Very appropriately and deservedly, he was honored as the inaugural recipient of UBC’s graduate teaching award in 1992.

Paul’s scientific contributions include over 300 refereed scientific papers, and he is one of the most cited authors in biological oceanography. His work was much broader than phytoplankton, and he co-authored “The Bible” of seaweed physiology and ecology; investigated the impact of large-scale iron fertilization experiments in the North Pacific on primary productivity, the impacts of pollution and nutrient enrichment from sewage treatment, nutrient cycling and climate change. His scholarship has attracted many honors, including being elected a Fellow of the Royal Society of Canada, and a recipient of the Timothy R. Parsons Medal. Despite all of the accolades, Paul always remained humble and well-grounded, and was always the first to put the achievements of others above his own. He was truly inspirational.

He left UBC in 2002 to direct the program in Atmospheric and Marine Science at Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, and help build the reputation and the faculty associated with marine science at HKUST. As well as instigating foundational research and inspiring researchers in Hong Kong, he cultivated the growth of biological oceanography and coastal marine science in China. His work was some of the first in the region exploring red tides, dead zones, and the role of the ocean in reducing global warming and climate change.

He returned to UBC in 2010 as Professor Emeritus, and continued to be as active as ever. He published nearly 50 papers in the last five years, mentored students and junior faculty, and promoted the research and reputations of his trainees and colleagues. He continued to organize and teach courses for advanced students and postdocs, and provide advisory and leadership roles to national and international scientific committees and government agencies as an authority on water quality and

supply, marine resources, climate change impacts and environmental protection. His voice and perspective will be sorely absent.

Paul will be greatly missed by those he touched, but especially by Victoria, his wife of 51 years, and their children Rachel, Richard and Christina.

A scholarship fund that has been set up in Paul's memory and is accepting donations can be found at: <http://memorial.supporting.ubc.ca/paul-j-harrison/>.

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During his visit, Dr. Cembella shared his knowledge on the biotransformation of toxins in clams. RedFAN also partially supported the participation of some of its members in the 17th International Conference on Harmful Algae held in Brazil in October 2016. In this event, the Mexican bid, presented by Christine Band Schmidt (CICIMAR), was the winner to become the local organizer of the 19th International Conference on Harmful Algae. RedFAN will be involved in the organization of this important event that will be held in Los Cabos, B.C.S., Mexico in October 2020.

In 2015 RedFAN gave partial financial support to some members for attending the third congress of SOMEFAN (Mexican Society for the Study of HABs) and in 2017 it will be an important support for the organization of the 4th Congress of the Society which will be held together with the 2nd Meeting of the Latin American Association for the Study of Harmful Algae (ALEAN) in October in Cancun, Quintana Roo, Mexico (www.somefan.org).

Further, the RedFAN published a *state of knowledge* book in Spanish, de-

tailing the incidence of HABs, effects, ecology, taxonomy and physiology in Mexico. The book chapters are authored by members of RedFAN. In addition, a bulletin with news on HAB occurrence and RedFAN activities is published periodically. As part of the dissemination tasks, a contribution on HAB topics was published in the national newspaper *La Jornada*, and a webpage about RedFAN (Spanish and English) developed (<http://redfan.cicese.mx>; Fig. 1). RedFAN looks forward to the consolidation of an interdisciplinary working group in a short time to prepare a National Program to deal with HAB events in Mexico.

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Keynote Presenters announced for 11th ICMSS in Galway

11TH ICMSS
IRELAND
International Conference on
Molluscan Shellfish Safety
GALWAY 14-18 MAY 2017

The International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety, organized by the Marine Institute in Galway, Ireland will take place from 14th May to 18th May 2017 at the National University of Ireland, Galway. The conference provide an opportunity to bring together experts from all over the world to exchange ideas, information and the most up to date findings, allowing us to review current state of the art and future prospects in molluscan shellfish safety. Keynote presentations from Dorothy Jean McCoubrey (Public Health Specialist, New Zealand), Jim Oliver (University of North Carolina, USA), Andy Turner (Cefas Weymouth, UK), Don Anderson

(Woods Hole, USA), Jan Vinjé (Centers for Disease Control, Atlanta USA), Ana Gago-Martinez (EU Reference Laboratory for Biotoxins, Vigo, Spain), Philipp Hess (Ifremer, Nantes France) and Robert Atmar (Baylor College of Medicine Texas USA) will set the tone for what promises to be an exciting and timely conference.

Topics including risk assessment approaches, molecular techniques, emerging toxins and regional events will be presented in over 150 presentations, and an additional day of Science Café presentations on the Friday 19th will allow for a hands on relaxed format to present, discuss and explore

advancement in HAB methods, LC-MS/MS Technology and Regulatory Matters. In addition to the HAB and Toxin issues there is a full theme of Microbiological and Virus sessions, and many of these are plenary to promote a level of cross pollination between disciplines!

No week in Galway would be complete without experiencing the hospitality that the west of Ireland is renowned for, and a full programme of social activities will be provided. The organising committee are very pleased with the standard of submitted presentations and these will be presented in plenary, parallel and poster sessions. Attendees will have the opportunity to see first-hand the latest research and developments in our field and discuss and collaborate with colleagues from all around the globe. To register for the conference please go to www.ICMSS2017.com.

11th International Conference on Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates

The University of Bordeaux (France) is the organiser of the 11th International Conference on Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates, DINO11, which will be held from 17 to 21 July 2017 at Bordeaux, France. This series of conference was first held in 1978 in Colorado Springs, Colorado (United States) (DINO1) and the 11th DINO meeting will be held for the first time in France.

Dinoflagellates and their cysts have shown major research interest for both, biologists working with modern dinoflagellates and geologists working with fossil dinoflagellates. From a biological

viewpoint, this major plankton group has major interests in their taxonomy, genetics and ecology, and particularly in the study of toxic dinoflagellates (e.g. *Alexandrium*, *Dinophysis*) that can

endanger human health through intoxication of shellfish or other organisms higher up the food chain. From a geological viewpoint, fossils dinoflagellate cysts are routinely used in biostratigraphy and palaeoclimatological applications. The international conference DINO11 will serve as a platform for exchanges between biologists and geologists concerning all these themes.

More information can be found on: <http://www.laplif.org/dino11/calquedino11.htm>

2017 Gordon Research Conference on Mycotoxins & Phycotoxins

Understanding the Exposure and Global Health Risks Associated with Naturally Occurring Environmental Biotoxins in a Rapidly Changing World

This meeting will be held from 18-23 June, 2017 at Stonehill College, Easton, MA, United States. Chairs: Kathi Lefebvre & Paul Turner.

If you have any questions or would like further information, please contact Megan Totten (mtotten@grc.org)

Additionally, a Gordon Research Seminar will be held in conjunction with the above GRC. The Mycotoxins & Phycotoxins GRS is scheduled to take place from June 17-18, 2017 at Stonehill College, Easton, MA and will be chaired by Katherine Perri & David McMullin.

Website: <http://www.grc.org/programs.aspx?id=14794>

SAHFOS 4th International Marine Phytoplankton Taxonomy Workshop

An IOC sponsored workshop to be held from 3 to 14 July 2017 at the Sir Alister Hardy Foundation for Ocean Science (SAHFOS), Plymouth, Devon, United Kingdom.

This workshop is aimed at early career scientists, technicians, postgraduates and marine ecologists with a basic knowledge of marine phytoplankton. This interactive workshop focuses on

the identification of key marine phytoplankton found in North Atlantic and European waters.

A combination of seminars and hands-on practicals led by internationally renowned experts covering sampling techniques, settling and slide preparation, cell counting, isolation and microscopy and culturing.

Please note the application deadline

for the 2017 course has passed, and the workshop is fully subscribed.

More information can be found at the SAHFOS website: <https://www.sahfos.ac.uk/> (Training Courses and Workshops)

Contact: djoh@sahfos.ac.uk

IOC Qualifications in Identification and Enumeration of Harmful Marine Microalgae

A now traditional IOC course on identification of harmful marine microalgae, including optional workshops on enumeration and culture techniques.

The 2017 course will be held from 6 to 19 August at the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae in Copenhagen, Denmark.

Since 1993 the IOC has conducted training courses on harmful microalgae. The purpose has been to improve the taxonomic and identification skills of the participants for research purposes and for practical monitoring of harmful algal blooms. The course includes 100 hours of teaching and is divided into two parts.

- The first part of the course is an internet teaching programme giving general introductions to the various

groups of harmful algae; this part is mainly for self-study and estimated to 40 hours of reading.

- The second part is a practical course in species identification including 2 optional workshops in enumeration and culture techniques (see tentative programme below). It may be possible to participate in both workshops, or alternatively spent the time examining mixed samples from various geographical regions and/or own samples. Part 2 includes 60 hours of teaching and a microscope will be available to each participant during the entire period.

From 2006 the IOC training in HAB identification has been offered within a new framework which gives accredita-

tion. The present course includes now a practical exam at the end of the course with an IOC Certificate of Proficiency in Identification of Harmful Algae issued to participants who pass the exam. We know by experience that many of the more than 500 trainees we have had over the years have wished the courses to give accreditation, and in some countries, the IOC courses have become a reference for laboratories to be approved for carrying out regulatory monitoring for harmful microalgae.

Detailed information on the course can be found in "Upcoming Events" at the IOC website: <http://hab.ioc-unesco.org/>

Session on Ciguatera at the 10 IPFC

A theme session on ciguatera, *Ciguatera fish poisoning in the Indo-Pacific region: incidence, toxin dynamics, impacts on socio-ecosystems, and risk management*, will be held at the **10 Indo-Pacific Fish Conference (10 IPFC)**, 2-6 October 2017, Tahiti, French Polynesia (<https://ipfc10.criobe.pf/>).

Organizers: Mireille Chinain, Susanna Piovano, Jean Turquet, Marie-Yasmine Dechraoui-Bottein (mchinain@ilm.pf; susanna.piovano@usp.ac.fj; Turquet.arda@orange.fr; M-Y.Bottein@iaea.org)

The Ciguatera session (H5) is planned as part of Theme H (The Future of Fish and Human Interactions). The call for abstract is now open: <https://ipfc10.criobe.pf/program/call-for-abstracts/>

Scope: Fish products are the nutritional basis of many island populations globally. Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) results from the consumption of fish that have accumulated ciguatoxins (CTXs) produced by benthic dinoflagellates in the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa*. Over the past decades, the frequency and distribution of CFP have increased significantly in the Indo-Pacific region, a likely consequence of

Photo from Institut Louis Malarde, French Polynesia, in Clausing et al, IOC Manual and Guides 59, 2016

numerous environmental changes in coastal and lagoon ecosystems. Despite increased knowledge about the impacts of climatic cycles and biogeography of *Gambierdiscus*, ciguatera events are still very difficult to predict. Likewise, the uptake, tissue distribution, accumulation and toxicity of CTXs in fish are still poorly understood. The existence of numerous structural variants (conge-

ners) of the toxin, and the lack of a duly validated reference test for CTXs both constitute a major obstacle in the sustainable exploitation of fish resources. In addition to the direct effects of ciguatera on public health and the economy of nations highly dependent on fish consumption, the fear of ciguatera often leads to reduced fishing in many indigenous Pacific populations, which reminds us that the impact of ciguatera risk must also be examined from sociological and societal perspectives and not only from a public health standpoint. Recently, several initiatives to implement a more efficient management of CFP risk globally have emerged within the scientific community. The main objective of this session is to present the recent advances in these research fields and to foster networking between scientists and stakeholders concerned with seafood safety.

Expected Audience: The targeted audience includes researchers (biologists, eco-toxicologist, modelists, economists, etc.) and managers interested in marine biotoxins and seafood safety issues. A group of 20 attendees from the Pacific region, Japan, Europe, and La Réunion is expected.

Taxonomic Note

Alexandrium catenella vs. *A. fundyense*
The Nomenclature Committee for Algae has decided (Prud'homme van Reine, 2017) that the name *Gonyaulax catenella* (*Alexandrium catenella*) should not be rejected and that *A. fundyense* and *A. catenella* are conspecific having nomenclatural priority the name *A. catenella*.

Prud'homme van Reine, 2017, *Taxon* 66 (1): 191-192. [<https://doi.org/10.12705/661.16>]

Alexandrium catenella from Huichas Islands, Aysén, Chile. Micrograph from Pablo Salgado.

Oceanography special issue

The March 2017 *Oceanography* special issue on *International Cooperation on Harmful Algal Bloom Science* will be available online by the end of March. The table of contents can be found at <https://tos.org/oceanography/issue/volume-30-issue-01>

Articles in this issue synthesize achievements and identify pending questions within different Core Research Projects from the SCOR-IOC GEOHAB Programme (2000-2013). The recently launched new programme, GlobalHAB, is introduced.

Eds-in-chief

Beatriz Reguera, IEO, Vigo, Spain
Eileen Bresnan, Marine Scotland Science, Marine Laboratory, Scotland, UK

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

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